

Deriving Fine-structure constant from a charged plank particle

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Abstract: Most forms of equivalent fine-structure constant definitions uses quadratic terms dependent on elementary charge ($\propto e^2$). There are alternate forms which avoids quadratic dependence, but these typically are defined using at least three different quantities, like the one $\alpha = \frac{c\mu_0}{2R_K}$. In this paper we try to derive fine-structure constant, which would not have any exponent in expression and would be defined using a pair of quantities only.

For that one needs to consider charged plank particle with $+e$ charge, which radius is approximately equal to plank length. Such particle is pictured below :

Now, lets define electric potential energy $U_{cpp}(r)$ of negative elementary charge, placed at such micro black-hole surface, which will be :

$$U_{cpp} = -k_e \frac{e^2}{r_p} \quad (1)$$

, where r_p is plank length. Using such definition of charged plank particle electric potential energy, one can arrive at simple definition of fine-structure constant :

$$\alpha = \frac{|U_{cpp}|}{E_p} \quad (2)$$

, where E_p is plank energy, or mass-energy of charged plank particle so to say. Substituting physical values into electric potential energy expression of charged plank particle (1) one can find out that $U_{cpp} \approx 1.43 \times 10^7 J$. Which gives fine structure constant within 0.15% error bounds.

Conclusions: Fine structure constant can be derived using only two quantities - charged plank particle electric potential energy near it's surface and same particle total mass-energy, so called plank energy with small relative error , eq (2). From that follows fine-structure constant basic interpretation - it shows how much electric potential energy near charged micro black hole surface is weaker than it's energy stored in self-mass.